

Comparative study of copper precursors for synthesis of CuO nanoparticles by ultrasonic-assisted thermal decomposition method

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Abstract : In this work, CuO nanoparticles were synthesized by an ultrasonic assisted thermal decomposition method using different copper precursors including copper acetate (Cu-A), copper nitrate (Cu-N) and copper chloride (Cu-C). The sample synthesized by copper acetate (Cu-A) was consisted of finer and more uniform particles than copper nitrate (Cu-N) which resulted in a wider band gap. On the other hand, copper chloride as a precursor resulted in a plate-like morphology. In comparison with the bulk CuO, the Cu-A sample showed a larger band gap which was attributed to its particle size. It was concluded that different copper precursors have significant effects on the particle size, morphology as well as the band gap of the final powder.

Keywords : Copper oxide, nanoparticles, ultrasonic-assisted method, thermal decomposition, band gap.

Introduction

Nanoparticles have been actively studied for their size- and shape-induced novel properties. In recent years, the synthesis and production of nanomaterials has received much attention due to their excellent physical and chemical properties in comparison with their bulk counterparts. Also they have potential applications in nanocomposite materials and nanoscale devices as interconnectors for nanoelectronics¹⁻³. Among these materials copper oxide (CuO), a p-type semiconductor with a narrow band gap, has been studied intensely because of its numerous applications in catalysis, semiconductors, batteries, sensors and field transistors⁴⁻⁷. On the other hand, large fractions of the surface area, excellent stability and good electric properties have guided to new studies to determine its applicability as a material for solar cells, in particular due to its photoconductivity and photochemical properties⁸. Furthermore nanocrystalline p-type metal oxide semiconductors of Cu are of special interest because of their efficiency as nanofluids in heat-transfer applications. It has been reported that addition of 4% CuO improves the thermal conductivity of water by 20%.

Recently, various methods such as sonochemical method, sol-gel technique, one-step solid state reaction method at room temperature, electrochemical method, thermal decomposition of precursors, and co-implantation of metal and oxygen ions have been reported for the preparation of nanocrystalline p-type metal oxide semiconductors^{9,10}. Conventional methods for the preparation of CuO powders include one step solid state reaction at room temperature, mechanical milling of commercial powders and so on. However, none of these methods seem to be suitable for the preparation of highly dispersed CuO nanoparticles, which has been found to be an obstacle for many applications, especially in catalysts and electrodes.

Gandhi *et al.*¹¹ reported the ultrasound assisted synthesis of nano-sized CuO using copper acetate and concentrated hydrochloric acid. Cu(OH)₂ nanowires have been prepared by ultrasound assisted solution route using Cu₇Cl₄(OH)₁₀·H₂O as a precursor and hierarchical CuO nanowires were obtained by thermal transformation of the Cu(OH)₂ nanowires¹². Kumar *et al.*¹³ developed a sonochemical method to prepare CuO nanoparticles, but

severe conditions of reaction and excessive toxic organic solvents were needed in this method.

Despite considerable efforts devoted to the preparation of the nanosized CuO¹¹⁻²¹, there is a lack of information about ultrasonic-assisted preparation methods. The effect of initial precursor on the final band gap, morphology and grain size of nanosized CuO has not been reported yet. In the present work, we report the ultrasonic-assisted synthesis and characterization of CuO nanoparticles using three different copper precursors including copper acetate, copper nitrate and copper chloride.

Results and discussion

XRD patterns of synthesized samples are shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen that in all samples, monoclinic CuO phase has been obtained according to JCPDS 41-0254

$$t = \frac{0.9\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (1)$$

where t is the crystallite size, λ the wavelength of X-ray radiation ($\text{CuK}\alpha$), θ the Bragg angle and β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the most intense diffraction peak. The calculated crystallite sizes for these three samples were represented in Table 1.

It can be seen that the crystallite size for Cu-A and Cu-N obtained by this method ranges between 20–25 nm. However, Cu-C has yielded finer crystallites, i.e. 11.74 nm which is in good accordance with its XRD pattern. In comparison with Cu-A and Cu-N samples, Cu-C has broader peaks. On the other hand, the intensity of XRD peaks is more or less the same for all the three samples which reveals that the crystallinity has not been dependent on the nature of the copper source.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of CuO samples synthesized via ultrasonic-assisted method.

(space group $C2/c$) and no impurity peaks are observed except for Cu-N in which some Cu_2O exist as an impurity. Based on previous reports, the sample heat treated at 300 °C which is the minimum temperature for the removal of the organic residuals. At higher temperatures, grain coarsening would be occurred and the grain size increases. The crystallite sizes were calculated using Debye-Scherrer equation :

Table 1. Crystallite sizes and band gap values of CuO samples synthesized from different copper sources

Sample	Crystallite size (nm)	Band gap (eV)
Bulk CuO	-	1.85 ²²
Cu-A	23.85	2.5
Cu-N	20.68	1.57
Cu-C	11.74	2.6

FTIR spectra of Cu-A, Cu-N and Cu-C samples were shown in Fig. 2. In the FTIR spectra, peaks at about 3430 cm^{-1} are ascribed to the stretching mode and H-O-H bending vibration of the free or absorbed water. Cu-C

larger agglomerated spherical particles are obtained for Cu-N. However, the morphology of particles for Cu-C sample is completely different and agglomerated plate-like particles are observed. In general, the ultrasonic as-

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of synthesized samples via different precursors.

sample exhibits two obvious absorption peaks at around 498 and 602 cm^{-1} , which can be attributed to vibrations of Cu-O bond. However, these two peaks are overlapped and a single peak at around 534 cm^{-1} for Cu-A and 536 cm^{-1} for Cu-N are observed. Weak peaks in the range of $1000\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the FTIR spectra indicate that residual organic compounds have not been removed completely after calcination process at $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 h.

FTIR spectra have long been utilized as a powerful tool to provide supplementary information on the nature of copper oxides²³. Absorption peaks around 480 and $530\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be assigned to the vibrations of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-O}^{23\text{--}25}$. So it is evident that CuO has been formed in all three samples which are in good agreement with XRD results.

SEM images of Cu-A, Cu-N and Cu-C samples were shown in Fig. 3. Agglomerated spherical nanoparticles (less than 100 nm) are observed for Cu-A sample, while

larger agglomerated spherical particles are obtained for Cu-N. However, the morphology of particles for Cu-C sample is completely different and agglomerated plate-like particles are observed. In general, the ultrasonic as-

isted synthesis method has provided CuO nanoparticles in which the final morphology is dependent on the initial copper source. Semispherical and plate-like morphology of the samples are confirmed by TEM images shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen that for Cu-A sample, particles were mainly smaller than 100 nm , however for Cu-N sample, particles larger than 100 nm were also observed. Furthermore, CuO plates in Fig. 5(c) are hardly agglomerated. Consequently, it is difficult to make an exact measurement of their sizes, but as a rough estimation, they range between $80\text{--}120\text{ nm}$ in length and $10\text{--}40\text{ nm}$ in width.

Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern of the Cu-N sample is shown in Fig. 5(d). Diffraction dots and diffuse rings of different lattice planes in the SAED pattern is in good accordance with XRD results and the monoclinic system.

The structure of copper precursors including copper

Fig. 3. SEM images of (a) Cu-A, (b) Cu-N and (c) Cu-C samples.

acetate, copper nitrate and copper chloride is mainly different which can affect the quality of the final product. In the copper acetate structure one oxygen atom on each acetate is bound to one copper atom. The two copper atoms are separated by only 2.65 Å, which is close to the Cu-Cu separation in metallic copper. The two copper centers interact resulting in a diminishing of the magnetic moment. Therefore, it is essentially diamagnetic due to cancellation of the two opposing spins. Copper nitrate structure is mainly a fully 3D coordination polymer net-

Fig. 4. TEM images of (a) Cu-A, (b) Cu-N, (c) Cu-C samples and (d) the SAED pattern of Cu-N sample.

works with infinite chains of copper(II) centers and nitrate groups. In copper chloride structure the copper centers have distorted octahedral geometry due to the Jahn-Teller effect. Chlorides bridge asymmetrically to Cu centers.

In addition to structural differences of the copper precursors, in Cu-N sample using copper nitrate as precursor nitrates tend to develop large amounts of nitrogen oxide gases during the calcination process. Toxicity that occurs due to a sudden release of these gases is the key unfavorable reason why the nitrate precursor is recommended less.

UV-Vis spectrophotometry was used to characterize optical absorption properties of obtained CuO samples. Optical absorption spectra of synthesized samples are shown in Fig. 5. For measurements, the obtained powders were dispersed in deionized water and sonicated for 20 min to form a homogeneous suspension with the concentration of about 0.1 g/L. It is obvious that for Cu-A and Cu-C there is a broad absorption peak at about 300–410 nm which is in good agreement with previous re-

Fig. 5. Optical absorption spectra of the CuO samples. The inset shows the weak adsorption peak of the Cu-N sample.

ports^{9,26}. The inset in Fig. 5 shows the weak adsorption peak for Cu-N. The adsorption edge for all samples is at about 250 nm. It has been confirmed that the size and morphology of nanoparticles have some effects on their UV-Vis spectra.

The absorption band gap E_g can be calculated using the following eq. (2) :

$$(\alpha h\nu)^n = B(h\nu - E_g) \quad (2)$$

where $h\nu$ is the photo energy, α is the absorption coefficient, B is a constant relative to the material and n is either 2 for a direct transition or 1/2 for an indirect transition²⁷. The plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ for the synthesized samples in deionized water is shown in Fig. 6. The band gap of CuO nanoparticles is calculated and listed in Table 1. It can be seen that for Cu-A and Cu-C nanoparticles, band gap values were larger than the reported values for the bulk CuO ($E_g = 1.85 \text{ eV}$ ²²). Finite size effects have been reported as being responsible for the enlargement of band gap values of nanoparticles^{28,29}. But for Cu-N nanoparticles, this value is smaller than bulk CuO.

Experimental

All reagents were of analytical grade and were used without further purification. Three different samples were

synthesized by different copper sources. Detailed description of the preparation step is as follows and also summarized in Table 2.

Copper acetate precursor (Cu-A) :

50 ml of fresh aqueous ammonium carbonate solution (0.3 M) was quickly added to 300 ml of aqueous copper acetate ($\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$) solution (0.05 M) under ultrasonic agitation which was continued for 20 min. The precipitated deposit was washed and dried at 60 °C for 3 h. Then, the dried powder was heat treated at 300 °C (5 °C/min) for 4 h.

Copper nitrate precursor (Cu-N) :

3.18 g oxalic acid and 12.15 g copper nitrate were dissolved in 200 ml deionized water. The copper nitrate solution was ultrasonicated for 5 min. Then, the oxalic acid solution was added dropwise under ultrasonic agitation. After 15 min ultrasonication and keeping the mixture constant at room conditions, a pale blue deposit was formed which was separated from the upper transparent phase, washed with ethanol and deionized water, and centrifuged. The final bluish white powder was dried at 60 °C for 3 h and then calcined at 300 °C (5 °C/min) for 3 h.

Table 2. Detailed description of the preparation routes of CuO nanoparticles

Sample	Copper source	Additives	Ultrasonic agitation	Drying	Calcination	Color of final powder
Cu-A	Copper acetate	Ammonium carbonate	20 min	60 °C, 3 h	300 °C, 4 h	Black
Cu-N	Copper nitrate	Oxalic acid	20 min	60 °C, 3 h	300 °C, 4 h	Black
Cu-C	Copper chloride	PEG ^a +6 M NaOH	20 min	60 °C, 3 h	-	Brown

^aPolyethylene glycol.

Fig. 6. $(\alpha hv)^2$ versus $h\nu$ curves for synthesized samples.**Copper chloride precursor (Cu-C) :**

Polyethylene glycol (PEG 1000, 0.8 g/ 300 ml deionized water) was mixed with copper chloride (0.57 g/ 500 ml deionized water) aqueous solution for 15 min in an ultrasonic bath. By adding drops of 6 M NaOH solution, the color of the mixture converted from blue to dark

brown. The mixture was kept constant at room conditions for 15 min and then it was ultrasonicated for another 30 min in hot water (78–81 °C) to complete the reaction. The precipitated brown deposit was extracted by centrifuging. The obtained powder was dried at 60 °C for 3 h.

X-Ray powder diffraction (XRD) was performed on a Philips PNA-analytical diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54178 \text{ \AA}$). FT-IR spectra (450-4000 cm^{-1}) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum One spectrophotometer with KBr pellets. SEM micrographs were obtained on a LEO 1455VP scanning electron microscopy. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were obtained using a Philips CM-120. Electronic spectra were recorded by CARY 100 Bio VARIAN UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

Conclusions :

It could be concluded that nanosized CuO has been successfully synthesized under current mild experimental conditions of ultrasonic-assisted preparation method using different copper precursors including copper acetate, copper nitrate and copper chloride. It was shown that initial copper sources have major effects on the morphology, particle size and optical properties of the final CuO nanoparticles. Among synthesized samples, Cu-A had the smallest and the most uniform semispherical nanoparticles. Hence, Cu-A sample exhibited the best optical properties. In comparison with the bulk CuO, the Cu-A sample had bigger band gap which was attributed to its nanosized particles. The adsorption edge for all the samples was at about 250 nm.

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References

1. Y. Xia, P. Yang, Y. Sun, Y. Wu, B. Mayers, B. Gates, Y. Yin, F. Kim and H. Yan, *Adv. Mater.*, 2003, **15**, 353.
2. C. N. Rao, G. U. Kulkarni, P. J. Thomas and P. P. Edwards, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2002, **8**, 29.
3. W. Wang, I. Germanenko and M. Samy El-Shall, *Chem. Mater.*, 2002, **14**, 3028.
4. A. Chowdhuri, V. Gupta, K. Sreenivas, R. Kumar, S. Mozumdar and P. K. Patanjali, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 2004, **84**, 1180.
5. S. Pande and T. Pal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **87**, 405.
6. A. Umar, M. M. Rahman, A. Al-Hajryc and Y. B. Hahn, *Electrochem. Commun.*, 2008, **11**, 278.
7. X. G. Zheng, C. N. Xu, Y. Tomokiyo, E. Tanaka, H. Yamada and Y. Soejima, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2000, **85**, 5170.
8. R. A. Zarate, F. Hevia, S. Fuentes, V. M. Fuenzalida and A. Zuniga, *J. Solid State Chem.*, 2007, **180**, 1464.
9. X. Zhang, D. Zhang, X. Ni and H. Zheng, *Solid-State Electron.*, 2008, **52**, 245.
10. D. Li, Y. H. Leung, A. B. Djuricic, Z. T. Liu, M. H. Xie, J. Gao and W. K. Chan, *J. Cryst. Growth*, 2005, **282**, 105.
11. S. Gandhi, R. H. H. Subramani, T. Ramakrishnan, A. Sivabalan, V. Dhanalakshmi, M. R. Gopinathan Nair and R. Anbarasan, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 2010, **45**, 1688.
12. L. Zhu, Y. Chen, Y. Zheng, N. Li, J. Zhao and Y. Sun, *Mater. Lett.*, 2010, **64**, 976.
13. R. V. Kumar, Y. Diamant and A. Gedanken, *Chem. Mater.*, 2000, **12**, 2301.
14. J. F. Xu, W. Ji, Z. X. Shen, S. H. Tang, X. R. Ye, D. Z. Jia and X. Q. Xin, *J. Solid State Chem.*, 1999, **147**, 516.
15. C. Carel, M. M. Bahout and J. C. Gaude, *Solid State Ionics*, 1999, **117**, 47.
16. C. K. Xu, Y. K. Liu, G. D. Xu and G. H. Wang, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 2002, **37**, 2365.
17. D. Chen, G. Z. Shen, K. B. Tang and Y. T. Qian, *J. Cryst. Growth*, 2003, **254**, 225.
18. Y. Chang and H. C. Zeng, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2004, **4**, 397.
19. B. Balamurugan, B. Mehta and S. Shivaprasad, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 2001, **79**, 3176.
20. N. D. Hoa, N. V. Quy, H. Jung, D. Kim, H. Kim and S. K. Hong, *Sens. Actuators (B)*, 2010, **146**, 266.
21. X. C. Jiang, T. Herricks and Y. N. Xia, *Nano Lett.*, 2002, **2**, 1333.
22. J. I. Pankove, "Optical Processes in Semiconductors", Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1971.
23. C. A. Melendres, G. A. Bowmaker, J. M. Leger and B. J. Beden, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1998, **449**, 215.
24. D. H. Sullivan, W. C. Conner and M. P. Harold, *Appl. Spectrosc.*, 1992, **46**, 811.
25. G. Kliche and Z. V. Popovic, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1990, **42**, 10060.
26. M. Kaur, K. P. Muthe, S. K. Despande, S. Choudhury, J. B. Singh, N. Verma, S. K. Gupta and J. V. Yakhmia, *J. Cryst. Growth*, 2006, **289**, 670.
27. C. T. Hsieh, J. M. Chen, H. H. Lin and H. C. Shih, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 2003, **83**, 3383.
28. V. K. Jain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 123.
29. I. Das, Y. Singh, N. R. Agrawal, S. A. Ansari and S. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 171.

